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RESULTS OF THE QUESTIONNAIRE SURVEY ON IMPROVING THE SPECIAL PHYSICAL TRAINING OF FEMALE FOOTBALL PLAYERS

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Abstract

This article presents the results of a questionnaire survey conducted with top coaches of the Uzbekistan Super League. The survey focuses on what changes should be introduced to the training and competition processes to improve the specialized physical preparation of female football players.

Keywords: *top coaches, football experts, competition period, female physiology.*

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada O'zbekiston Superligasining top murabbiylari bilan anketa so'rovnomasi o'tkazilgan bo'lib, unga ko'ra futbolchi qizlarning maxsus jismoniy tayyorgarligini takomillashtirish uchun mashg'ulot hamda musobaqa jarayoniga qanday o'zgartirish kiritilishi kerakligi haqida so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: *top murabbiylar, futbol bo'yicha mutahassislar, musobaqa davri, ayollar organizmi.*

Аннотация

В данной статье были изучены мнения специалистов по совершенствованию уровня специальной физической подготовленности высококвалифицированных футболисток. Полученные результаты свидетельствуют о необходимости внесения изменений в их тренировочный процесс.

Ключевые слова: *специальная физическая подготовка, специалист, анкетирование, физическая нагрузка.*

Introduction. In order to study the opinion of specialists on the use of means and methods aimed at improving the level of special physical training of highly qualified female football players and on the planning of loads, we first of all developed a questionnaire, in which coaches must answer questions related to assessing the level of development of basic physical abilities of female athletes, their significance in increasing the effectiveness of competitive activity, and the contribution that each of them makes.

Objective: To conduct a questionnaire survey among experts regarding the issue of enhancing the specialized physical preparation of highly skilled female soccer players.

Research Methods and Organization. The questionnaire consists of 10 questions, a certain part of which provides for simple answers consisting of personal opinions of football coaches on the organization, planning, and implementation of tools and methods used to improve the level of special physical preparedness in the training process (Table 1).

Table 1

QUESTIONNAIRE

Last name _____
 Place of work _____
 Length of service _____
 Mentoring License _____

No.	Questions	Response	
		Yes	No
1.	Do you think the special physical training of female football players in Uzbekistan is at a high level?		
2.	Do you think the level of special physical preparedness of female soccer players depends on the structure of training loads?		
3.	Is it necessary to increase the level of special physical training of female football players during the competition?		
4.	Is it possible to increase the level of special physical fitness of female soccer players in the inter-game cycle through table games?		
5.	Is it necessary to make changes to the methodology for developing the level of special physical training of highly qualified female football players?		
6.	Is it possible to increase the level of special physical training by increasing the proportion of strength and speed-strength loads?		
7.	Is it possible to use strength and speed-strength loads in the weekly cycle of the competition period, similar to those used in the training of men's teams?		
8.	Is it possible to use strict training regimens characteristic of men's teams in the training of women's teams?		

9.	Is it possible to use non-specialized means to improve the level of special physical fitness of female soccer players in the weekly inter-game cycle of the competition period?		
10.	Is it possible to increase the level of special physical fitness of female soccer players during competitions only through complex-oriented loads?		

This questionnaire also includes several questions that coaches need to answer on which stages of the annual cycle it is advisable to plan workloads in the above-mentioned direction (Pic. 1).

Pic. 1. Percentage of responses received according to the questionnaire

Now we will dwell on the detailed disclosure of the main problematic issues and difficulties identified as a result of questionnaires conducted among football coaches. The experts' answers were as follows:

- 21 respondents, i.e., 87.5% of football coaches who participated in the survey, believe that at the present stage "the level of special physical training of highly qualified female football players is not sufficiently high";
- 83.3% of coaches believe that the level of special physical preparedness of female football players is inextricably linked with the structure of training loads;
- 79.1% of respondents noted that during the competition period, it is necessary to regularly carry out work aimed at increasing the level of special physical fitness of female football players;
- 52% of coaches indicated that it is possible to increase the level of special physical training of female soccer players in inter-game cycles at the expense of table games;

- 76% of respondents agreed with the need to make changes to the methodology for developing the level of special physical fitness of highly qualified female football players;

- 44% of respondents support the use of strength and speed-strength loads in the weekly cycle of the competition period, similar to those used in the training of men's teams;

- 36% of coaches voted in favor of planning a strict training regime with strength and speed-strength loads in the inter-game cycles of the competition period;

- 52% of participants indicated that non-specialized means can be used in the weekly inter-game cycle of the competition period to improve the special physical fitness of female football players;

- 64% of coaches believe that special physical training of female soccer players can be improved only through complex-oriented loads during competitions.

Analysis of the respondents' answers shows that there are serious contradictions in the opinions of football specialists on this issue.

In the course of their activities, football specialists encountered difficulties in answering questions related to the means, methodological techniques, approaches, forms of organizing training and planning loads used in the process of special physical training, which indicates insufficient attention to this issue in practice.

Analysis of the results of a survey conducted among football specialists shows that more than half of the respondents prefer to increase the level of special training through control and official matches. This, in turn, confirms that coaches do not have a deep approach to the issue of choosing training loads to improve the level of special training.

The main part of the coaches had difficulty answering the question about the use of special and non-specialized means used to improve the level of special training of female football players, which indicates that the coaches who participated in the survey did not have sufficiently deep knowledge of theoretical approaches to solving this problem.

The majority of coaches have mechanically transferred the tools and methods used in the training of men's teams to the planning of special training for women's teams.

The conducted survey made it possible to identify the following problems, different opinions, and methodological approaches faced by football coaches regarding the organization and implementation of the methodology of special training for highly qualified female football players:

- the presence of a "gap" between theory and practice on the issues of special physical training of female soccer players;

low awareness of the specifics of the formation and development of various special physical qualities aimed at improving the level of special training of female football players;

insufficient knowledge of the use of a wide range of specialized and non-specialized tools and methodological approaches in planning workloads aimed at increasing the level of special training, with adjustments when necessary.

Conclusion. Based on the foregoing, it can be said that the conducted questionnaire survey showed the relevance of the research problem and the practical necessity of its study.

REFERENCES

1. Абрамова Т.Ф., Озолин Н.Н., Геселевич В. А. и др. Современные представления о научных основах тренировки женщин //Всероссийскому научно-исследовательскому институту физической культуры и спорта 60 лет. Сборник научных трудов. - М., 1993. - С. 183-194.
2. Саенко И. В. Программирование тренировочных нагрузок на этапах макроцикла подготовки футболисток высокой квалификации. Автореф. Дис. ...канд.пед.наук. М.2002. – 22с.
3. Каримов Ф.Ж. Контроль уровня уровня специальной физической подготовки футболисток высокой квалификации // Вестник НУУЗ (УзМУ) 2022 1/2/1. –С. 126-129.
4. Каримов Ф.Ж. Анализ уровня физической работоспособности у футболисток высокой квалификации // “Fan-sportga” - ilmiy-nazariy jurnal 2023/8. –С. 18-210.
5. Karimov F.J. The analysis of the special training level of the players of a female football team U-16 // Mental enlightenment scientific – methodological journal. Vol. 5 No. 02 (2024). –P. 138-142.
6. Ahmedov, Farruh and Gardasevic, Novica and Setiawan, Edi and Olimov, Alisher and Muqimov, Olimjon and Jamoliddin, Komilov and Khuriyat, Khudaiberdieva and Yusupov, Rakhimjon. Comparison of technical and tactical parameters for elite judo athletes based on weight and gender categories // Ibero-American Journal of Exercise and Sports Psychology. Volume 19. 28.12.2024. P:502-506
7. Komilov, J., Isaeva, G., Jonzokova, S., Nosirova, D., & Suleymanova, R. (2021). Innovative approaches of psychological training of young sportsmen to the competitions. *Ilkogretim Online*, 20(3).